

Reinvestigation of Condensation of Resorcinol and β -Ketoester in the Presence of Polyphosphoric Acid. Synthesis of a Novel Coumarin Dimer

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THE synthesis of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin (**1**) by Pechmann condensation of resorcinol and ethyl acetoacetate with different condensing agent (i.e. I_2 , Br_2 , concentrated H_2SO_4 , PCl_5 , $POCl_3$, P_2O_5 and $AlCl_3$) is well-known¹. The present paper deals with the reinvestigation of synthesis of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin by the condensation of resorcinol and ethyl acetoacetate (in different molar ratio) using catalytic amount of polyphosphoric acid (PPA)². A new minor coumarin dimer (**2**) alongwith **1** was obtained (Scheme 1). The increase in the molar ratio of ethyl acetoacetate

Scheme 1

lead to a slight increase in the yield of the coumarin dimer **2** (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **1** AND **2**

Reaction temp. = 80°, Reaction time = 20 min		Yield (%)	
Molar ratio (mmol) Resorcinol : Ethyl acetoacetate (R : E)		1	2
1 : 1.0		63.5	13
1 : 1.5		67.8	21.4
1 : 2.0		66	25
1 : 2.5		65	28

The product **2**, m.p. 305°, $C_{20}H_{16}O_6$, showed the molecular ion at m/z 352 and a base peak at

m/z 45; ν_{max} 3 450, 3 275, 1 745, 1 690, 1 620, 1 580 and 1 510 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} 230, 380, 315 and 345 nm. The 1H - ^{13}C nmr data of the compound support the proposed structure. The presence of CH_2 group in compound **2** was confirmed by DEPT (distortion less enhancement through polarisation transfer) experiment.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-408 spectrophotometer, uv spectra on a Pye-Unique PU 8800 spectrophotometer and 1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra on a Bruker MSL 300 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

The coumarin dimer (2). General method: Polyphosphoric acid was prepared by mixing orthophosphoric acid (15 ml) and phosphorous pentaoxide (23.5 g) followed by heating on a water-bath for 1.5 h. A catalytic amount of polyphosphoric acid (160 g) was added to resorcinol (11 g, 100 mmol) and ethyl acetoacetate (13 ml, 100 mmol). The mixture was heated on a water-bath (75–80°) for 20 min with stirring. The viscous mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and the resulting solid (18 g, m.p. 180°) was crystallised from EtOH to yield compound **1** (7 g) which was characterised as 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin by comparison with authentic sample. The mother liquor showed the mixture of two bands I and II (tlc, silica gel, benzene-ethyl acetate 2 : 1). A portion (250 mg) of the mixture obtained from mother liquor was subjected to preparative thin layer chromatography on silica gel (benzene : ethyl acetate 2 : 1) and to yield **1** (100 mg) and **2** (55 mg). The same experiment was repeated with different molar ratio of ethyl acetoacetate (Table 1).

The coumarin dimer (2): It showed m.p. 305° (Found : C, 67.68; H, 4.70. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6$ calcd. for : C, 68.18; H, 4.54%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 450, 3 275, 1 745, 1 690, 1 620, 1 580 and 1 510 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 230, 280, 315 and 345 nm; 1H nmr δ H(CD_3OD , 300 MHz) 1.78 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.05 (3H, s, CH_3 group), 2.60 and 3.98 (each 1H, d, J 15.5 Hz, CH_2), 5.99 (1H, s, H-3), 6.45 (d, J 2.4 Hz, H-8'), 6.60 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.4 Hz, H-6'), 6.60 (1H, s, H-8), 6.88 (1H, s, H-5), 7.06 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-5'); ^{13}C nmr 170.45 and 163.48 (C=O), 160.88, 158.26, 158.26, 156.53, 153.15 (oxygen bearing carbons), 104.47, 104.77, 111.70, 112.94, 113.00 (upfield aromatic carbons), 122.54, 125.92, 128.31, 129.53

(low field aromatic carbons) which account for total 19 out of 20 carbons ; one carbon may be overlapping, 25.39 and 18.14 ($2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 41.48 (4'-C), 41.26 (CH_2) ; m/z 352 (104.47), 338 (26.94), 337 (20.95, $M-15$), 334 (3.58), 323 (2.69), 309 (8.97, $M-15-28$), 294 (6.88), 276 (2.69), 266 (4.19), 260 (2.69), 250 (6.88), 244 (2.69), 234 (8.38), 229 (4.34) and 226 (3.58). On the basis of these data it was characterised as coumarin dimer 2.

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